

MODERN METHODS AND APPROACHES TO THE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH SENSORINEURAL HEARING LOSS

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Abstract. *The article discusses modern treatment methods for children with various forms of hearing impairment (conductive hearing loss, sensorineural hearing loss, auditory neuropathy, central auditory processing disorders), as well as technical and surgical methods for compensating hearing deficits. It presents the organization of comprehensive rehabilitation for children with hearing impairments, which includes medical, technical, and psychological-pedagogical rehabilitation methods, implemented on three levels: macro-level (government), meso-level (scientific centers of otorhinolaryngology, audiology, hearing aid fitting; medical and pedagogical universities), and micro-level (local audiological and rehabilitation centers, maternity hospitals, clinics, educational institutions).*

Keywords: *sensorineural hearing loss, auditory neuropathy, central auditory processing disorders, treatment methods for hearing loss in children, compensation methods for hearing impairments in children, hearing aids, comprehensive rehabilitation for children with hearing impairments.*

Relevance. Currently, significant progress has been made in the rehabilitation of children with sensorineural hearing loss due to the development and implementation of various treatment methods, compensatory techniques, and a comprehensive approach to rehabilitation. All methods of rehabilitation for children with hearing impairments can be divided into three groups: 1) medical; 2) technical; 3) psychological-pedagogical.

Medical Rehabilitation Methods. Medical methods include numerous conservative and surgical treatments, as well as compensatory techniques for various forms of hearing loss.

Therapy for Sensorineural Hearing Loss. Abroad, sensorineural and neurosensory hearing loss are distinguished. According to this classification, sensorineural hearing loss primarily involves damage to the hair cells of the cochlea. Neurosensory hearing loss encompasses all disorders related to the auditory perception process and, accordingly, the damage to auditory system structures from cochlear hair cells to the auditory cortex of the brain. Thus, sensorineural hearing loss is a subset of neurosensory hearing loss. In Russia, the term "neurosensory hearing loss" is officially used (the term "sensorineural hearing loss" is not entirely correct as a synonym). This group primarily includes patients with damage to auditory receptors—the cochlear hair cells.

Damaged hair cells do not recover in chronic forms of the disease. However, children are typically prescribed regular courses of medication aimed at preserving residual hearing. This is justified by the fact that, firstly, 30% of children experience progressive hearing loss in the first years of life. Secondly, a significant portion of children with hearing loss have conditions resulting from pregnancy and childbirth complications, with a high proportion of premature infants among them. In these cases, treatment involving medication and physiotherapeutic procedures that

improve cochlear blood circulation and metabolic processes in hair and nerve cells positively impacts the auditory and speech motor centers of the brain, enhancing the child's reactions to sounds and supporting the development of spoken language.

In cases of acute sensorineural hearing loss due to hair cell damage from circulatory disturbances, hypoxia, or intoxication, treatment initiated in the first hours and days after onset can restore hearing in 70-80% of patients. Therapy focuses on improving cochlear blood flow, relieving intoxication, enhancing the metabolism of hair and nerve cells, and includes dehydration therapy, glucocorticoids, microcirculation agents, spasmolytics, detoxifying agents, antihistamines, sedatives, central nervous system metabolites, and anticholinesterase drugs [1, 2, 4]. In young children, it is typically impossible to determine the onset of the disease, which is why acute sensorineural hearing loss often progresses to a chronic form.

Surgical methods for the therapy, or rather, compensation of sensorineural hearing loss, include the implantation of hearing aids (for mild to moderate hearing loss) and cochlear implantation (for deafness) [3, 5].

Currently, intensive research is underway to develop new promising methods for treating hearing impairments:

1. Regeneration of lost hair cells in sensorineural hearing loss using stem cells.
2. Use of cochlear implants (CIs) for delivering medications to the cochlea:
 - To reduce trauma to the cochlea and preserve residual hearing during cochlear implantation (corticosteroids—dexamethasone);
 - To enhance the effectiveness of CIs—introducing substances that stimulate the growth of auditory nerve fibers to CI electrodes, stimulating the regeneration of outer hair cells;
 - To stimulate the growth of auditory nerve endings using neurotrophins.
3. Gene engineering—replacing mutated genes in germ cells that cause various genetic, including hereditary, hearing impairments.

Technical Rehabilitation Methods. Undoubtedly, the development of modern approaches to the rehabilitation of children with hearing impairments has been significantly influenced by research in auditory physiology and the advancement of technology. First, devices have emerged that enable the objective assessment of physiological responses in different parts of the auditory system and facilitate the differential diagnosis of hearing impairments in children from the earliest days of life [6, 7]. This has created conditions for very early rehabilitation of children with hearing impairments, which is crucial considering the critical period for speech development. Second, sound amplification and transmission technology has advanced, allowing for the creation of hearing aids and other devices designed to compensate for any degree of hearing loss (I, II, III, IV degree of hearing loss, deafness) of various types (conductive, neurosensory, mixed hearing loss, auditory neuropathy, central auditory processing disorders). Most children with hearing loss use behind-the-ear hearing aids. Hearing aids have been developed for very young children, equipped with protection against accidental adjustments, algorithms for suppressing acoustic feedback (whistling), and automatic volume control. In adolescence, children with mild to moderate hearing loss may also use in-ear hearing aids. It is also important that technologies have been developed for adjusting hearing aids for very young children who cannot communicate their sensations [8-10].

For children who cannot wear standard behind-the-ear or in-ear hearing aids (e.g., due to atresia of the external auditory canal or chronic otitis media), implantable hearing aids have been

developed. These include bone conduction hearing aids such as Baha, Bone Bridge, Alpha, and Ponto.

With modern hearing aids, children with II, III, and even IV-degree hearing loss can hear soft sounds and even whispers [5, 8, 10].

Psychological-Pedagogical Rehabilitation Methods. Hearing impairment in a child leads to disturbances in the development of the second order (speech development), third order (development of thinking due to underdeveloped speech), and fourth order (formation of emotional-volitional processes due to underdeveloped speech and thinking). The goals of psychological-pedagogical rehabilitation for children with hearing impairments are to prevent or minimize the consequences of poor hearing, i.e., the development of secondary disorders. Historically, psychological-pedagogical rehabilitation was primarily aimed at compensating for hearing impairments through preserved sensory analyzers, in contrast to medical rehabilitation, which focuses on restoring auditory function. In recent years, the advancement of medical and technical rehabilitation methods for children with hearing impairments has significantly influenced psychological-pedagogical approaches. First, thanks to the introduction of newborn hearing screening and very early diagnosis of hearing impairments, the age at which psychological-pedagogical rehabilitation begins has significantly decreased. It now starts from the moment of identifying a hearing impairment, i.e., from the first month of the child's life. Second, with early hearing aid fitting with digital hearing aids and cochlear implants, even deaf children today can hear all speech sounds, including whispers, meaning they can learn to understand speech and communicate through hearing rather than sight. This fundamentally changes the methodology for teaching speech to deaf children—the modern approach is based on developing their hearing with hearing aids/cochlear implants to a level close to normal, enabling them to spontaneously acquire speech as typically hearing children do. Third, while earlier the deaf educator typically focused only on the child, now the target of psychological-pedagogical intervention includes the family alongside the child [11]. This is due to the fact that small children spend a large part of their time at home and that both hearing and deaf children with hearing aids/cochlear implants acquire speech by interacting with their parents during daily activities and joint play. Thus, the main tasks of specialists are to teach parents to create opportunities and needs for their child to constantly hear and communicate verbally. This involves ensuring that the child always wears well-adjusted hearing aids/cochlear implants, monitoring the child's hearing through them, communicating with the child who does not yet understand or speak, helping the child remember sounds and words, and encouraging them to use their voice and speech for communication.

Comprehensive Medical-Psychological-Pedagogical Rehabilitation of Children with Hearing Impairments. The diversity of therapy and compensation methods for hearing impairments in children necessitates the organization of a comprehensive medical-technical-pedagogical rehabilitation system that must consider the following:

1. The rehabilitation process for a child with hearing impairments takes many years.
2. Rehabilitation occurs in institutions of various departmental affiliations (healthcare, education, social protection).
3. Various specialists (doctors, special educators, engineers, etc.) participate in rehabilitation and must collaborate to achieve effective rehabilitation outcomes.
4. The family actively participates in the rehabilitation of a child with hearing impairments.

Within such a system, three levels should be distinguished:

1. Macro-level (government);
2. Meso-level (scientific centers of otorhinolaryngology, audiology, hearing aid fitting; medical and pedagogical universities);
3. Micro-level (local audiological and rehabilitation centers, maternity hospitals, clinics, educational institutions).

Macro-level (government). At this level, the overall objectives of government policy regarding the rehabilitation of children with hearing impairments and its financial support are determined. This involves not only the Ministry of Health but also the ministries of social protection and education. Their tasks include, for example:

1. Conducting newborn hearing screenings.
2. Allocating funds for purchasing hearing aids and cochlear implant systems, surgical treatment, equipping hearing centers, rehabilitating children post-cochlear implantation, training specialists, and ensuring the existence of special educational institutions and inclusive education.
3. Legislative acts that ensure the continuity of policies related to the rehabilitation of children with hearing impairments, among others.

Meso-level (scientific centers of otorhinolaryngology, audiology, hearing aid fitting; medical and pedagogical universities). Medical centers implement high-tech treatment methods for children (e.g., hearing-improving surgeries using middle ear implants, cochlear implants, etc.). New methods for the therapy and rehabilitation of children with hearing impairments are developed in medical centers and universities. Their tasks also include training specialists from the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Education, initiating organizational and legislative activities in health, social protection, and education that are necessary for the rehabilitation of children with hearing impairments.

Micro-level (maternity hospitals, clinics, audiological/rehabilitation centers, educational institutions, associations of parents of children with hearing impairments). This level is where the main rehabilitation of children with hearing impairments occurs—newborn hearing screening, differential diagnosis of hearing impairments, fitting children with hearing aids, regular monitoring of hearing status, technical support for hearing aid/cochlear implant users (tuning and replacement), developing individual development programs for children and the conditions for their implementation, conducting deaf pedagogy sessions for the development of hearing, speech, and communication skills, teaching hearing-impaired children, providing professional assistance to children during inclusive education, and offering psychological support to children and their families.

Public organizations of parents of children with hearing impairments are increasingly playing a crucial role in the rehabilitation system in many countries, including Russia. They organize rehabilitation centers for children with hearing impairments, training seminars for parents and specialists, and prepare various legislative initiatives for local and federal government support for these children.

In the country, newborn hearing screening is implemented, and the number of children diagnosed in the first months of life is increasing; binaural hearing aid fitting for children and cochlear implantation for deaf children are being carried out; standards for medical assistance to these children are being developed; and educational programs allowing children with hearing impairments to study in regular schools are being established.

Conclusion. Currently, thanks to the development of medical, technical, and psychological-pedagogical methods, the possibilities for rehabilitating children with hearing impairments have significantly expanded. Modern technical means and medical technologies enable many hard-of-hearing and deaf children to hear, thus providing them with the potential to learn to understand speech and communicate. This allows children with hearing impairments to fully integrate into hearing society—they can study alongside hearing children, receive a good education, and eventually find employment. A significant number of children with hearing impairments are already enrolled in regular kindergartens and schools. The foundation for the integration of children with hearing impairments into hearing society is early rehabilitation. This includes:

- Early detection and diagnosis of hearing impairments in children (2-4 months);
- Therapeutic interventions (from the moment of diagnosing the hearing impairment);
- Early binaural fitting of hearing aids for children (for bilateral neurosensory hearing loss with hearing thresholds over 40 dB, at ages 2-6 months);
- Regular hearing monitoring (every 6 months), as many children experience hearing deterioration in the early years and thus require retuning or replacement of their hearing aids;
- If a child has significant hearing loss or deafness, cochlear implantation may be necessary (optimal age is 10-18 months);
- Sessions with a deaf educator focusing on developing the child's hearing, thinking, and oral speech (from the moment the hearing impairment is detected), including training parents on developing their child's hearing, thinking, and oral speech during daily activities.

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